

Gender Commonality in the Upregulated Transcriptome of Patients with Ischemic Stroke

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The present study systematically searched the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) DataSets for and retrieved the GSE22255 dataset that included transcriptomic data from Ischemic Stroke patients. This was an expression profiling by array using peripheral blood mononuclear cell samples. The mRNAs with adjusted P-value < 0.05 and $\log_2FC \geq 2$ were deemed as significant Differentially Expressed Genes (DEGs). DEGs were compared between and within gender subjects from patients in reference to control groups.

When male stroke patients were compared with male controls, the top upregulated gene was the C-X-C motif chemokine Ligand 3 also known as CXCL3 ($\log_2FC = 6.77$, P value= 2.73×10^{-6}). Likewise, when female stroke patients were compared over female controls, the top upregulated gene was again CXCL3 ($\log_2FC = 3.83$, P value=0.035). However, the CXCL3 gene ($\log_2FC = 5.15$, P value= 8.98×10^{-4}) was found to be significantly upregulated in male over female patients with stroke.

CXCL3 plays a key role in neuroinflammation by acting as a chemoattractant for neutrophils. This analysis provides evidence of CXCL3 as a marker for ischemic stroke in both genders but men have more severe neuroinflammation in acute ischemic attack. Laboratory studies are needed to validate the gender commonality of CXCL3 expression in stroke.

Table-1: Descriptors of GEO DataSet.

Gene Expression Series (GSE) ID	Author	Year	Platform	IS Samples	Control Samples	IS/Control Ratio
GSE22255	Krug et al.	2011	Affymetrix Human Genome U133 Plus 2.0 Array	20	20	1

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